

From pictures to numbers: Multi-species seabird surveys using drone imagery and neural networks

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ABSTRACT

Seabirds are among the most threatened avian taxa globally, with over half of all species in decline. Accurate population estimates are essential for tracking trends and informing conservation, yet traditional survey methods are limited by logistical challenges, high costs, and the potential for wildlife disturbance, particularly in remote coastal areas. Unoccupied aerial vehicles (UAVs or drones) offer an efficient and low-disturbance alternative, but the vast volumes of imagery they produce are often labour-intensive to analyse.

In this study, we combined drone imagery with deep learning techniques to estimate colony size and abundance of surface-nesting seabirds based on counts of visible individuals. High-resolution aerial imagery was collected from 163 colonies along the southern and central Norwegian coastline over three breeding seasons (2022–2024), covering a total of 7.67 km². A convolutional neural network (Faster R-CNN with ResNet-101 backbone) was trained on 131 annotated orthomosaics and evaluated on 32 additional annotated orthomosaics from geographically distinct colonies.

Across all data, 23,062 individual seabirds were annotated. Colonies hosted an average of 141.5 ± 193.9 individuals and 4.1 ± 2.3 focal species per site. At a confidence threshold of 0.7, the model achieved a detection rate of 87.5 % and a macro F1-score of 0.88. It performed well across multiple focal species, including terns, gulls, and cormorants, and remained robust in mixed-species colonies. Most errors involved false negatives or confusion among visually similar species.

Our results demonstrate the potential for deep learning models to support efficient, scalable, and low-disturbance seabird monitoring across diverse habitats, reducing manual annotation effort and informing conservation practice.

1. Introduction

Reliable population estimates are essential for understanding trends in wildlife abundance, informing conservation efforts, and maintaining the ecological functions that species provide. This is particularly urgent for seabirds, which are among the most threatened avian taxa globally: over one-third of seabird species are classified as threatened, an additional 11 % are listed as near threatened, and more than half are experiencing population declines (Rush et al., 2018, Dias et al., 2019, BirdLife International, 2024). These declines are driven by multiple, often interacting pressures, including invasive species at breeding sites, fisheries bycatch, and climate change (Croxall et al., 2012; Dias et al.,

2019). Reflecting the severity of these threats, monitored seabird populations have declined by approximately 70 % since 1950 due to human activity (Palczyński et al., 2015). In Norway, where a long and complex coastline provides vital breeding habitat for numerous seabird species during the summer months, populations are mirroring global trends and experiencing significant declines (Fauchald et al., 2015). While selected populations are monitored semi-regularly through the SEAPOP program (www.seapop.no) and other governmental initiatives, many colonies remain unmonitored due to logistical and financial constraints. Addressing these ongoing declines requires improved, large-scale monitoring approaches that are both accurate and feasible to implement.

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Seabird populations are inherently difficult to survey, as many species nest in remote or inaccessible locations, such as steep cliffs or offshore islands, which limit opportunities for conventional survey methods. Standard approaches typically involve colony walk-throughs using sample plots, transects, or entire colony counts, in which observers traverse breeding sites on foot to count the number of breeding pairs or active nests (e.g. Bird et al., 2022; Hutto et al., 1986). These methods, however, are time-consuming, costly, and often restricted to small spatial and temporal scales (Paleczny et al., 2015). Moreover, ground-based surveys can cause significant disturbance to the birds, potentially resulting in reduced reproductive success, pair separation, heightened intraspecific aggression, increased predation of eggs and chicks, and higher rates of nest abandonment (Blackmer et al., 2004; Carney and Sydeman, 1999). Birds may also be overlooked, especially in areas with dense vegetation or rugged terrain, and thus underestimate population estimates (Hodgson et al., 2018). Occupied aircraft surveys can cover broader areas but are expensive and may produce images of insufficient quality for species-level identification, particularly of smaller or less abundant birds, although image quality can be improved through appropriate camera and lens selection (Edney and Wood, 2021; Hayes et al., 2021; Rodgers Jr et al., 2005). While some uncertainty in population counts is unavoidable, inaccurate estimates can have significant consequences for conservation decisions and actions.

The use of drones (unoccupied aerial vehicles, UAVs) in wildlife monitoring, conservation, and ecological research has expanded rapidly in recent years (Chabot and Bird, 2015; Mo and Bonatakis, 2022). For seabird studies, drones offer several advantages: they can access remote or otherwise inaccessible locations (Hayes et al., 2021), collect high-resolution imagery within short timeframes (Pfeifer et al., 2019), offer cost-effective monitoring (Valle and Scarton, 2019) and, when operated responsibly, cause minimal disturbance to wildlife (de Leija et al., 2023; Rush et al., 2018; Valle and Scarton, 2021). Drone imagery provides a permanent record that can be reviewed, independently verified, or reanalyzed using improved methods. In addition to eliminating observer bias linked to differences in surveyor experience in traditional surveys (Diefenbach et al., 2003), drones can facilitate more accurate and consistent population estimates (Hodgson et al., 2018). However, drone-based surveys also generate vast quantities of data. Manually identifying and labelling wildlife in the images is therefore a labour-intensive task, which can span several weeks depending on the dataset's size (Kellenberger et al., 2021).

To address the bottleneck of manual image annotation, automated detection methods, particularly Object-Based Image Analysis (OBIA) and deep learning approaches, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are increasingly being used to detect and count birds in drone imagery (e.g., Hayes et al., 2021; Rush et al., 2018; Tyndall et al., 2024). For example, Kellenberger et al. (2021) used CNNs to count 21,000 terns in drone imagery, reducing the annotation workload from three weeks to just 4.5 h. These approaches not only save time, but also enable systematic, repeatable, and objective analyses that are less reliant on species-specific expertise. When combined with standardized drone surveys, CNN-based methods can ensure consistency across observers, locations, and survey periods. Yet despite their potential, such models still face limitations. The large volume of data created by drones requires substantial computational resources for processing, and the analysis demands specialized expertise and software (Edney et al., 2023). Moreover, many existing CNN-based models are tailored to detect only one or two species in specific environments, such as penguins (Pfeifer et al., 2019) or Antarctic shags (Cusick et al., 2024). In reality, many seabirds breed in mixed-species colonies and inhabit diverse geographic regions, highlighting the need for models that can effectively distinguish different species and generalize across locations.

The aim of this study was to improve population estimates of nesting seabirds using drone imagery and automated image analysis. To achieve this, our objectives were to (1) collect high-resolution drone imagery of surface-nesting seabird colonies, (2) train a deep learning model capable

of detecting and identifying seabird species in the imagery, and (3) evaluate the model's predictive and generalization performance across independent test locations representing a range of habitat types and species compositions. We addressed these objectives by developing and implementing a cloud-based detection pipeline designed to facilitate scalable and accurate monitoring of seabird colonies.

2. Methods

2.1. Locations and study species

This study was conducted along Norway's southern and central coastline during three field campaigns between 2022 and 2024 (Fig. 1). Survey sites included rocky islets, grassy slopes, and steep cliffs, habitats commonly used by nesting seabirds and representative of the region's natural variation in landscape structure, vegetation cover, and lighting conditions.

The region supports approximately 40 seabird species that breed during the summer months. For this study, we focused on surface-nesting species that are readily detectable in aerial RGB imagery. The focal species included European herring gull (*Larus argentatus*), great black-backed gull (*L. marinus*), lesser black-backed gull (*L. fuscus*), common gull (*L. canus*), black-headed gull (*Chroicocephalus ridibundus*), Arctic tern (*Sterna paradisaea*), common tern (*S. hirundo*), European shag (*Phalacrocorax aristotelis*), and great cormorant (*P. carbo*). These species typically nest in open, treeless areas with low vegetation (Jones et al., 2008), making them well suited for detection in high-resolution drone-based imagery (Rush et al., 2018).

Other seabird species, such as guillemots (family Alcidae) and the Atlantic puffin (*Fratercula arctica*), are also common in the study area. However, these species typically nest in concealed locations such as crevices, under boulders, or in burrows, which makes them difficult to detect using standard RGB sensors and are therefore excluded from this study.

2.2. Image acquisition

Data was collected during three comprehensive field campaigns in the breeding seasons of 2022, 2023, and 2024. In 2022, one team collected data in southwest Norway and the Oslo region between May 15 and June 22. In 2023, four teams covered sections of the southern coastline from May 15 to June 1, and in 2024, four teams surveyed the western coastline from May 18 to June 5 (Fig. 1). In all three years, each team consisted of two fieldworkers: one drone pilot and one bird ecologist. Each of the nine teams was assigned a specific coastal stretch, with the objective of surveying all islands and coastal areas on which our focal species were potentially nesting in colonies. In sheltered waters, teams typically used small open boats, while in more exposed areas, larger, chartered vessels were used to move between islands.

Survey periods were timed to coincide with the incubation stage, when most birds had laid eggs but before hatching had begun (Helberg et al., 2023). However, given the diversity in breeding phenology among the species, which include both early and late nesting seabirds, and the constraint that only one survey was conducted per year, the chosen time for completing the surveys was a compromise resulting in the best 'average' time window that captured the breeding period.

2.2.1. Drones and sensors

Surveys were conducted using six commercially available multirotor drones from DJI (Shenzhen, China): Mavic 3M, Mavic 3E, Mavic 2 Pro, Phantom 4 Pro, Mini 2, and Matrice 300 RTK (Table 1). The Mavic 3M and 3E drones were equipped with factory-fitted RGB cameras featuring a 4/3" CMOS sensor (20 MP, 5280 × 3956 pixels) and a 24 mm focal length lens. The Mavic 2 Pro and Phantom 4 Pro both carried 1" CMOS RGB sensors (20 MP, 5472 × 3648 pixels), while the Mini 2 used a smaller 1/2.3" CMOS sensor (12 MP, 4000 × 3000 pixels). The Matrice

Fig. 1. Seabird colony locations along the Norwegian coast included in this study. Marker colors indicate the year of data collection (2022, 2023, and 2024), while shapes distinguish between training and independent test datasets. The inset shows an example orthomosaic of a colony site, with a zoomed-in section highlighting individual seabirds marked by black bounding boxes.

Table 1

Summary of drone missions showing sensor resolution (megapixels), mean ground sampling distance (GSD, cm) with range in brackets, mean and total survey area covered (km²), and number of missions per drone model. All drones were equipped with factory-fitted RGB sensors, except the Matrice 300 RTK, which carried a Zenmuse P1 camera.

Drone model	Sensor resolution (MP)	Mean GSD (cm)	Mean area (km ²)	Total area (km ²)	No. of missions
DJI M3E	20.9	0.94 (0.3–1.3)	0.06	5.19	94
DJI M3M	20.9	0.86 (0.5–1.3)	0.06	1.73	31
DJI Mavic 2 Pro	20.0	0.72 (0.4–1.2)	0.02	0.47	24
DJI Mini 2	12.0	1.01 (0.7–1.2)	0.02	0.16	7
DJI Matrice 300	44.7	1.20	0.08	0.08	1
DJI Phantom 4 RTK	20.0	0.73 (0.5–1.3)	0.01	0.03	6

300 was equipped with a full-frame Zenmuse P1 camera (45 MP, 8192 × 5460 pixels, 35 mm lens). All drones except the Mavic 2 Pro and Mini 2 were outfitted with a Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) positioning module, enabling precise georeferencing and improved spatial accuracy during surveys.

In total, 163 drone missions were conducted across all platforms (Table 1; Table S1). While flight altitude was not consistently retained in flight logs across all platforms, we used ground sampling distance (GSD), which integrates sensor properties and flight geometry, as a measure of imagery resolution. Most surveys were conducted using the smaller

Mavic-series platforms to enable safe take-off and landing from small boats and confined island sites, where deployment of larger drones such as the Matrice 300 RTK was not feasible.

2.2.2. Drone flight protocol

We preprogrammed flight plans using DJI’s Pilot software (DJI; Shenzhen, China. v2.5.1.15), defining each survey area as a polygon with a 5–10 m buffer zone to ensure complete coverage of the island and a small part of the surrounding waterline. This buffer also minimised flight time, as our focus was on birds occurring on land. All flight plans followed a “lawn-mower” pattern (parallel back-and-forth flight lines) with the gimbal in nadir position. We aimed for 70–80 % side and frontal overlap between images to ensure sufficient coverage of consecutive flight lines to enable accurate stitching of individual images into final orthomosaics (Rush et al., 2018).

Disturbance responses can vary greatly among species, breeding stages, weather conditions, and approach angles (Edney et al., 2023), so we adopted a flexible, site- and species-specific approach rather than a fixed altitude threshold. To achieve the image resolution required for reliable identification while minimising disturbance, initial flight parameters varied by bird size. Generally, colonies with larger birds (e.g., cormorants and great black-backed gulls) were flown at 40 m above ground level (AGL) and a speed of 5 m/s; medium-sized species (e.g., common gull and lesser black-backed gull) at 30 m AGL and 3 m/s; and smaller species (e.g., terns and black-headed gull) at 20 m AGL and 1–3 m/s. Although these flight altitudes were below the general 50 m guideline (Edney et al., 2023), our operations followed the intent of best-practice recommendations through precautionary, adaptive flying based on local testing and continuous behavioural monitoring. This approach provided a practical balance between achieving sufficient image resolution and minimising disturbance under the logistical constraints of offshore island surveys. Within this framework, behavioural

responses were monitored qualitatively in real time as part of the adaptive flight approach, rather than recorded as standardized quantitative metrics. Future studies in which disturbance itself is a primary research focus could incorporate systematic behavioural scoring or disturbance indices to enable quantitative comparisons across species and sites.

Take-offs and landings were primarily performed from boats, launching the drone from the pilot's hand. To minimise disturbance to the birds, the boat remained at least 100 m from the colony (Edney et al., 2023), and the drone approached horizontally at the pre-set mission height and speed (Vas et al., 2015).

During the drone's approach and image capture, we continuously monitored the colony for reactions to the drone using binocular, such as birds leaving nests or flushing. If birds reacted, the mission was paused, and the drone was held in a stationary hover until the birds had resettled. Once the birds were back on their nests, the mission resumed with preprogrammed flight parameters. If the birds reacted again, adjustments were made to a higher flight altitude, slower speed, or both. In cases of serious negative responses, such as attacks on the drone or persistent flushing, the mission was cancelled, and the drone was immediately flown to a higher altitude before returning for landing. Additional information on the drone setup and flight procedures is available as a flight protocol (Arnberg and Molværsmyr, 2024).

All drone operations were conducted in accordance with Norwegian legislation and under the necessary permits. Permits for flights and landings within protected areas were obtained from the responsible management authorities (e.g., County Governors and National Park Boards) under §48 of the Nature Diversity Act (*Naturmangfoldloven*; <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2009-06-19-100>). Operations in restricted or controlled airspace complied with Norwegian Civil Aviation Authority regulations (in line with EU Regulation 2019/947), with flight permissions obtained through the NINOX online system or by direct coordination with local air traffic control. All drone pilots were certified under the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) Open Category for UAV operations.

2.3. Image processing

At the end of each field day, drone data were uploaded to SeaBee's MiniO storage using the SeaBee software FieldUploader (available at: GitHub - SeaBee-no/SeaBee-FieldUploader). This automatically restructured mission data into the format required by the SeaBee platform and generated configuration files needed to control downstream image processing. An automated server-side script continuously monitored the system for new uploads and triggered predefined image processing workflows. Full documentation of the pipeline is available on GitHub via the SeaBee Documentation repository (Sample et al., 2025).

Image processing was performed using OpenDroneMap (ODM; version 3.5.3 or 3.5.2, depending on upload year), an open-source photogrammetry software that produces georeferenced orthomosaics and reconstructs 3D structure from overlapping images using a structure-from-motion (SfM) algorithm. For each flight mission, this pipeline produced high-resolution orthomosaics and digital elevation products (DSM and DTM), though only the orthomosaics were used in the current study. Orthomosaics were generated with GSDs ranging from 4 to 13 mm, depending on flight altitude and sensor resolution (Table 1; Table S1). Final products were published to a public GeoNode server hosted at: <https://geonode.seabee.sigma2.no>.

All computed orthomosaics were resampled to a standardized GSD of 5 mm to ensure consistency across the dataset before applying the deep learning model(s). Each orthomosaic was divided into overlapping image patches of 3904 × 3904 pixels and stored as JPEG files. This procedure standardized image dimensions, optimized compatibility with standard deep-learning frameworks, and retained essentially all relevant visual details necessary for reliable species detection.

2.4. Annotation

Orthomosaics were annotated (labelled) using a custom interactive web platform designed specifically for managing and annotating seabirds in drone imagery. Using this interface, domain experts (ornithologists experienced with seabird identification) annotated each visible seabird by drawing rectangular bounding boxes and assigning species labels. While occasional uncertainties occurred due to occlusion or ambiguous visual characteristics, the annotations were consistently of high quality and served as reliable ground truth for deep learning model training and testing.

The annotation of the 163 orthomosaics required approximately two working weeks for one person (about 75 h). This estimate reflects the annotation work itself and does not include time spent on iterative improvements to the annotation workflow and platform. To rigorously evaluate model generalization and performance, a subset of 32 orthomosaics was carefully selected by domain experts to serve as an independent test dataset. These test orthomosaics came from geographic locations not represented in the training data, allowing for a more realistic assessment of model performance across novel environmental conditions (Fig. 1).

For modelling purposes, certain taxonomically or visually similar species were grouped into broader categories to reduce confusion and improve classification consistency. Specifically, Arctic and common terns were merged into a single *Tern* sp. class, while great cormorants and European shags were grouped as *Cormorant/Shag*. Species-specific annotation counts and dataset partitioning (training, validation, and testing) are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2

Summary of species-specific annotation counts and dataset partitioning across training, validation, and test datasets. Percentages of annotations in each split relative to the total sample size is shown in brackets. Only species with a total sample size greater than 50 are shown. Note that cormorants and shags are grouped as a single class (cormorant/shag), as are terns (terns sp.).

Species	Train	Validation	Test	Total sample size
Lesser black-backed gull	2904 (61.23 %)	784 (16.53 %)	1055 (22.24 %)	4743 (20.57 %)
European herring gull	2700 (61.74 %)	817 (18.68 %)	856 (19.57 %)	4373 (18.96 %)
Black-headed gull	2173 (54.39 %)	979 (24.51 %)	843 (21.10 %)	3995 (17.32 %)
Cormorant/shag	1939 (51.41 %)	961 (25.48 %)	872 (23.12 %)	3772 (16.36 %)
Great black-backed gull	1191 (64.52 %)	279 (15.11 %)	376 (20.37 %)	1846 (8.00 %)
Common gull	1038 (71.49 %)	217 (14.94 %)	197 (13.57 %)	1452 (6.30 %)
Tern sp.	613 (48.04 %)	413 (32.37 %)	250 (19.59 %)	1276 (5.53 %)
Greylag goose	351 (70.91 %)	21 (4.24 %)	123 (24.85 %)	495 (2.15 %)
Eider	257 (55.87 %)	90 (19.57 %)	113 (24.57 %)	460 (1.99 %)
Barnacle goose	198 (60.74 %)	106 (32.52 %)	22 (6.75 %)	326 (1.41 %)
Oystercatcher	56 (60.22 %)	13 (13.98 %)	24 (25.81 %)	93 (0.40 %)

2.5. Deep learning model

We employed Faster R-CNN (Ren et al., 2015), a widely used and robust deep learning architecture designed for simultaneous object localization (i.e., precise identification of seabird locations) and recognition (species identification; Axford et al., 2024). We specifically selected the Faster R-CNN model with a ResNet-101 backbone (He et al., 2016) implemented using PyTorch (Paszke et al., 2019). This model was chosen for its established performance in similar object-detection tasks, strong representational capacity, moderate computational requirements, and the availability of pre-trained weights from natural image datasets (here, ImageNet; Deng et al., 2009), facilitating efficient transfer learning.

To improve model generalizability, we applied realistic, yet conservative image augmentations during training. These included small random rotations ($\pm 20^\circ$), random scaling adjustments ($\pm 10\%$), horizontal and vertical flips, and variations in brightness, contrast, hue and saturation. Also, subtle Gaussian noise and blur effects were introduced to simulate variability in image quality. An initial padding step was included to prevent boundary artifacts from cropping after image rotation and scaling. In addition, we did not normalize or stratify imagery by UAV or sensor type. Inter-sensor variability was treated as natural augmentation, encouraging the model to learn robust features transferable across platforms.

To address class imbalance in the dataset, we implemented a weighted patch-sampling strategy, ensuring a more balanced representation of species across training samples. We computed sampling weights for each class based on their relative frequency, or more specifically using:

$$w_c = \frac{(n_c/N)^\alpha}{\sum_i (n_i/N)^\alpha}$$

where w_c is the weight of class c , n_c is the number of images containing that class, and N is the total number of annotated images.

Here, we heuristically selected $\alpha = 0.5$ as a balanced compromise between completely uniform class representation ($\alpha = 0$) and purely frequency-driven sampling ($\alpha = 1$). Empty images (images with no annotation), of which there were many, were limited to be selected 10% of the time. Although detailed hyperparameter tuning for α was not conducted, validation experiments indicated improvements over random sampling alone.

During model training, we included all annotated species, even those with limited data availability (Table S2). However, during inference (evaluation), species with fewer than 50 annotation examples were excluded, as their limited representation led to model confusion and overprediction. Furthermore, these species were not focal to this study, as they were primarily non-surface-nesting or non-colony-forming birds occasionally present in the imagery. Technically, this exclusion was implemented by ignoring the corresponding logits in the network output.

Hyperparameter selection, such as learning rate, epoch count, and score thresholds, was minimally tuned using the validation subset to ensure training stability and to detect signs of overfitting. Final model training employed the entire available training data. We trained our model using stochastic gradient descent (SGD) with a learning rate of 0.002, a total of 75 epochs, and a stepwise learning rate decay. Training time was approximately five days using a single NVIDIA RTX 4000 SFF Ada GPU, demonstrating that our approach is computationally modest, even at the training stage.

2.6. Model evaluation

Model performance was evaluated by comparing predicted bounding boxes against ornithologist-generated ground truth annotations (see Section 2.4). A prediction was considered as a True Positive (TP) if it

overlapped significantly (Intersection-over-Union, $\text{IoU} \geq 0.3$) with a ground-truth bounding box. Predictions that did not meet this IoU threshold or had incorrect species labels were classified as false positives (FP), while ground-truth birds not matched by any prediction were recorded as false negatives (FN). To prevent double-counting, each ground-truth bird could only be matched to one prediction. Because our goal was to quantify species-level detections and colony-scale counts rather than exact pixel-level localization, a permissive IoU threshold (0.3) was appropriate to avoid over-penalizing minor box placement differences for small individuals.

We evaluated the model performance using the standard metrics, precision, recall, and F1-score, where:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{TP}}{(\text{TP} + \text{FP})}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TP}}{(\text{TP} + \text{FN})}$$

$$\text{F1 score} = 2 \times \frac{(\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall})}{(\text{Precision} + \text{Recall})}$$

Given the class imbalance across species (Table 2), we report both the class-level F1-scores (calculated separately per species) and the macro F1-score, defined as the unweighted mean of F1-scores across all classes.

We adopted a conservative thresholding approach that prioritized precision over recall to minimise overestimation of colony size while maintaining high overall accuracy. Because our primary objective was to generate reliable and unbiased abundance estimates that are comparable across sites and years, false positives were considered more problematic than false negatives, as they can inflate colony size estimates and misrepresent population trends. Based on the performance of the validation dataset, a universal confidence score threshold of 0.7 was selected to balance precision and recall. This threshold maximised the macro F1-score across species (Fig. S1) and was used during evaluation of the test set.

3. Results

Over the three-year study period, drone surveys were conducted on 163 seabird colonies across 43 field days, totalling 21 h and 51 min of flight time. The mapped area spanned 7.67 km² in total, with survey coverage increasing from 0.45 km² in 2022 (34 colonies), to 1.71 km² in 2023 (27 colonies), and reaching 5.51 km² across 102 colonies in 2024. The mean colony sizes remained relatively consistent across years (ranging from 0.013 to 0.063 km²), with individual sites spanning from small islets (0.0002 km²) to larger colonies over half a square kilometre (0.57 km²).

In total, we annotated 23,062 seabirds, of which 21,457 belonged to the focal species (Fig. 2; Table 2). The most abundant taxa were gulls, with European herring gull and lesser black-backed gull comprising the majority of observations. On average, colonies contained 141.5 ± 193.9 individuals, though numbers varied widely, from single-bird detections to as many as 1347 birds in a single colony. Islands typically hosted 4.1 ± 2.3 focal species, indicating frequent multi-species nesting.

3.1. Overall model performance

The model was evaluated on the test dataset using a global confidence threshold of 0.7, chosen based on validation performance to balance precision and recall (Fig. S1). At this threshold, the model detected 4139 out of 4731 ground-truth birds (87.5% detection rate), of which 3822 (92.4%) were correctly classified at the species level. This resulted in a precision of 0.88 and a recall of 0.87, with a macro F1-score of 0.88 across species. Most false positives were eliminated at this threshold, reducing detections on background features by nearly 90%

Fig. 2. Distribution and annual counts of manually annotated seabirds for each focal species across surveyed colonies in coastal Norway from 2022 to 2024. Each panel includes a map (left) showing colony locations with annotated individuals, and a barplot (right) summarising total counts per year.

(from 1972 to 207; Fig. 3).

At lower confidence thresholds, the model detected nearly all birds but substantially overestimated colony size (by 47 % at threshold = 0; Table S3). Total count estimates remained stable within ± 10 % for

thresholds between 0.5 and 0.8, with a slight underestimation of 3.3 % at the selected global threshold (0.7). Beyond this range, higher thresholds progressively reduced recall, resulting in up to 18.5 % underestimation at confidence threshold = 0.9.

Fig. 3. Confidence score distributions for each species in the test dataset. The red dotted line marks the global confidence threshold (0.7) applied during evaluation, selected based on validation performance. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Inference time was approximately 1.5 s per 3904×3904 pixel patch on a single NVIDIA RTX 4000 SFF Ada GPU. Processing the entire test dataset of 32 orthomosaics took slightly over two hours.

3.2. Class-wise performance

The model performed best on species with distinctive morphology and strong representation in the training data. Terns (F1 = 0.97), black-headed gull (F1 = 0.95), and the cormorant/shag group (F1 = 0.87) were all classified with high precision and recall (Table 3). In contrast, performance declined for species with visually similar counterparts. Herring Gull (F1 = 0.81) and common gull (F1 = 0.62) were frequently confused, with many detections labelled as common gull actually corresponding to herring gull (Fig. 4), contributing to common gull's especially low precision (0.51). A similar but less pronounced confusion occurred between lesser black-backed (F1 = 0.82) and great black-backed gull (F1 = 0.89; Fig. 4).

Species with limited representation in the training data showed

Table 3

Species-specific precision, recall, and F1-scores on the test dataset, calculated using a confidence threshold of 0.7 applied to model predictions.

Species	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Black-headed gull	0.98	0.92	0.95
European herring gull	0.90	0.75	0.81
Common gull	0.51	0.81	0.62
Lesser black-backed gull	0.95	0.72	0.82
Great black-backed gull	0.87	0.91	0.89
Tern sp.	0.95	0.98	0.97
Cormorant/shag	0.95	0.80	0.87
Eider	0.42	0.67	0.53
Barnacle goose	0.84	0.96	0.89
Greylag goose	0.88	0.92	0.90
Oystercatcher	0.62	0.67	0.64

variable performance. Barnacle goose (F1 = 0.89) and greylag goose (F1 = 0.90) were classified with high accuracy, likely due to their distinctive size and shape. In contrast, oystercatcher (F1 = 0.64) and especially

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix showing the performance of the seabird species classification model. Rows represent the ground truth species, and columns represent predicted species. Diagonal cells represent correct classifications (true positives), while off-diagonal cells represent misclassifications. ‘Background FP’ captures false positives on background elements (overpredictions for each species) while ‘Background FN’ are birds missed by the model (false negatives). Green shading intensity reflects the proportion of correct predictions within each species row, with darker tones indicating higher classification performance. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

eider (F1 = 0.53) had lower performance, affected by both false positives and false negatives (Fig. 4).

3.3. Common error patterns

False negatives were the most frequent error type across species and occurred even for well-performing classes. For instance, the model failed to detect 201 lesser black-backed gulls and 145 cormorants/shags. These errors typically occurred in environments with low-contrast or visually complex backgrounds, such as gravel, small stones, or patchy terrain, where birds were partially obscured or visually blended into the background (Fig. 5c–d). A substantial proportion of these missed detections had confidence scores just below the 0.7 threshold. As shown in Fig. 3, lowering the threshold increases recall for several species, including lesser black-backed gull, but also results in higher false positive rates.

False positives, while reduced by thresholding, remained across all species (12.1 % of all detections). These errors commonly involved background features such as sea foam, reflective water, bedrock textures, or stones that visually resembled birds in size, shape, or tone (Fig. 5a–b).

Species misclassification was another consistent source of error, particularly between morphologically similar species. As described above, the model often confused Herring with common gulls, as well as lesser with great black-backed gulls (Fig. 5e–f). These errors likely stem

from a combination of visual overlap between species, variation in bird posture, and class imbalance in the training data.

Finally, although ground sampling distance (GSD) varied across the original orthomosaics (4–13 mm) due to differences in flight altitude and sensor settings, all images were subsequently resampled to a standardized 5 mm GSD before model inference. Visual inspection nevertheless revealed no clear relationship between the original GSD and model performance (Table S4). Occasional image imperfections, such as seam blurring, stitching artifacts, or local distortions, were also noted but appeared to contribute to only a small fraction of classification errors.

4. Discussion

Monitoring seabird populations in remote and complex environments remains a major logistical challenge for conservation efforts. Our study demonstrates that combining drone-based surveys with deep learning enables an efficient and scalable approach to seabird population estimation across diverse and visually heterogeneous habitats. The deep learning model performed well across rocky outcrops, vegetated slopes, and mixed-species colonies, suggesting that automated approaches can substantially expand seabird monitoring beyond a limited subset of sites.

Compared to previous studies, our model’s performance is

Fig. 5. Examples of common prediction errors made by the seabird detection and classification model. (a–b) False positives, where background features such as water reflections and sea foam (a) and shadows or rocks (b), were incorrectly identified as birds (magenta boxes). (c–d) False negatives, where birds were present but not detected by the model (red boxes), shown alongside correctly identified individuals (green boxes). (e–f) Species misclassifications between visually similar species: in (e), a European herring gull is incorrectly classified as a common gull, and in (f), a common gull is misclassified as a European herring gull. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

encouraging, particularly when considering its ability to detect multiple species across diverse and complex coastal habitats (Kellenberger et al., 2021; Wilkin et al., 2025). Over our three-year study, we surveyed 163 seabird colonies and annotated over 21,000 birds from focal species often in multi-species nesting contexts. For comparison, Cusick et al. (2024) reported near-perfect detection of Antarctic shags ($F1 > 0.98$) in visually homogeneous environments, and Hayes et al. (2021) achieved F1-scores above 0.92 in spatially concentrated black-browed albatross colonies. In contrast, our model achieved an F1-score of 0.88 across multiple species and habitat types which introduce greater visual and

ecological complexity.

Broader bird detection frameworks for multi-species classification (e.g. Weinstein et al., 2022; Xie et al., 2022) have typically been based on simpler image types or show reduced accuracy when applied to novel data without retraining. Notably, our model maintained strong performance without site-specific tuning, indicating it can generalize well across varying colony compositions and landscapes. This suggests that it may serve as a practical tool for improving seabird monitoring at broader spatial scales, at least within Norwegian coastal environments.

Model predictions must always be filtered using a confidence

threshold to balance false positives against recall. At very permissive thresholds, the model substantially overestimates bird numbers by approximately 47 % due to many background features being detected as birds. In our case, a global threshold of 0.7 substantially improved reliability, reducing false positives and resulting in a slight underestimation of total bird counts (-3.3 %). At this threshold, the model behaved conservatively (Hayes et al., 2021; Tyndall et al., 2024), prioritizing precision at the expense of recall. However, applying a uniform threshold across all species also led to the suppression of some true detections, with background false negatives (i.e. birds missed entirely by the model) remaining a frequent source of error. Implementing adaptive thresholding strategies, such as species-specific confidence thresholds, could, in principle, improve model performance by tailoring thresholds to individual taxa (Villon et al., 2020). For instance, lowering the threshold for lesser black-backed gulls could help recover missed individuals, while raising the threshold for eiders could reduce false positives (Fig. 3). However, in our dataset, total count estimates were relatively stable (within ± 10 %) across thresholds from 0.5 to 0.8, indicating that model performance was already robust to moderate changes in confidence level. Consequently, the potential gains from adaptive thresholding were limited.

The model struggled with visually similar species and underrepresented (minority) classes. Frequent misclassifications between herring gulls and common gulls were likely exacerbated by class imbalance, with herring gulls being much more prevalent in the training data. Eiders and oystercatchers, although not focal targets in this study, occurred sporadically and in low numbers. As a result, they were underrepresented in the training dataset, with only 347 and 69 samples respectively, and had correspondingly low model performance. Both species also presented specific visual challenges. For Eiders, pronounced sexual dimorphism divided this class into two visually distinct categories, limiting the model's ability to learn consistent features. Oystercatchers' small size and dark plumage made them difficult to distinguish against complex coastal substrates such as wet rocks and seaweed. These patterns mirror well-documented challenges with class imbalance and background confusion on ecological deep learning models (Delplanque et al., 2023a, 2023b; Oksuz et al., 2020).

A notable limitation of our approach is that it does not directly estimate breeding population based on the number of occupied nests or breeding pairs, which is the standard method in Norway and many seabird monitoring programs globally (Dierschke et al., 2022). Instead, our model detects and counts all visible individuals, regardless of breeding status. While nesting status can sometimes be inferred from aerial imagery based on posture, our model was not trained for this task, and distinguishing breeders from non-breeders is challenging even for expert annotators. For this reason, we prioritized species identification and individual counts. Estimating breeding pairs when nests cannot be directly counted, as in our study, typically requires species-specific correction factors or semi-supervised annotations. While these methods have produced accurate results for some species (Corregidor-Castro et al., 2022), they introduce uncertainty, as the ratio of individuals to nests can vary with species, colony density, stage of incubation, and time (Harris et al., 2015; Walsh et al., 1995). In our study, semi-supervised annotation, using the models' predictions to find all birds in the orthomosaics, before manually assigning them to the right class and breeding status, dramatically reduced the annotation time. To support future model development, we also annotated all individuals with activity where possible (e.g., on nest, on land, or in flight), providing a basis for training models capable of distinguishing nesting birds.

While the model performed robustly across most species and settings, several avenues remain for technical improvement. First, applying more advanced data augmentation methods such as background replacement (e.g., inserting annotated individuals into varied backgrounds), occlusion simulation, or lighting variation, could improve detection under diverse conditions. This could be particularly beneficial for visually

cryptic species like eiders or for individuals partially obscured by terrain features such as rocks or vegetation. Second, leveraging self-supervised pre-training on large, unlabelled drone image datasets could improve generalization beyond what is achievable with ImageNet-based transfer learning. Foundation model techniques, such as contrastive pretraining (Chen et al., 2020; Mañás et al., 2021) or masked image modelling (Cong et al., 2022; He et al., 2022), may allow the network to learn ecological visual features more relevant to aerial wildlife imagery prior to supervised fine-tuning. Third, exploring alternative model architectures could provide performance gains or enable more scalable deployments. While Faster R-CNN with ResNet-101 offered a practical balance of accuracy and resource use, newer approaches show promise. Transformer-based models for detection, such as DETR (Carion et al., 2020) and Swin Transformer (Liu et al., 2021), have demonstrated strong representational capacity and may improve classification of rare or visually similar species. At the same time, lightweight detectors designed for efficiency, like EfficientDet (Tan et al., 2020), YOLOv7 (Wang et al., 2022), and emerging point-based frameworks such as HerdNet (Delplanque et al., 2023a, 2023b) and POLO (May et al., 2024), enable faster inference and reduced annotation effort. While our aim was to establish a robust, well-documented baseline using a proven architecture, future work could evaluate such alternative models for their potential to further improve efficiency and scalability. Lastly, we limited hyperparameter tuning to a conservative set of adjustments. While this helped avoid overfitting and ensured stable training, it also reflected a pragmatic choice to focus resources on model development and dataset preparation rather than exhaustive optimization. Broader exploration of training schedules, anchor-box configurations, or loss functions may provide incremental gains, but we expect the largest improvements will come from expanded training data, consistent annotations, and targeted augmentation strategies.

Although the model detections still require review and validation by human experts, deep learning-based approaches substantially reduce the annotation workload compared to fully manual methods (Kellenberger et al., 2021; Tyndall et al., 2024). The current model can serve as a preliminary annotator within a semi-automated pipeline, accelerating the annotation process by enabling experts to rapidly validate and correct model outputs. This is particularly valuable given the time-consuming nature of manually locating all birds in large aerial images. Notably, the first test models identified in some cases birds missed by manual annotators on the first couple of annotation passes, which were all annotated before the final model was trained. Considering the full monitoring workflow, drone-based surveys paired with deep learning models dramatically outperform traditional manual seabird surveys in both efficiency and wildlife disturbance. This can free considerable resources to expand survey coverage and frequency, ultimately enhancing conservation efforts.

5. Conclusion

Over the three-year study period, we surveyed 163 seabird colonies and annotated over 21,000 birds from focal species, providing one of the most extensive drone-based seabird datasets in northern Europe. The deep learning model developed here demonstrated strong performance across a range of complex and visually heterogeneous coastal habitats, successfully detecting the majority of birds at species level. By combining drone surveys with AI-based detection, our study contributes to the ongoing evolution of seabird monitoring, where these technologies can improve detection accuracy, reduce survey time with minimal disturbance to birds, and support standardized, repeatable monitoring across large geographic areas. Such approaches are increasingly vital for understanding population trends in coastal ecosystems, which face growing pressures from climate change, human activity, and habitat loss. Scalable tools like those demonstrated here can provide the high-resolution data needed for adaptive management and informed decision-making in conservation (Edney et al., 2023).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mie P. Arnberg: Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Are Charles Jensen:** Software, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **James Sample:** Software, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Arnt-Børre Salberg:** Software, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing. **Kasper Hancke:** Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Hege Gundersen:** Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Sindre Molværsmyr:** Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2025.103583>.

Data availability

All SeaBee data products, including orthomosaics and model predictions, are publicly available at geonode.seabee.sigma2.no. Manual annotations, model predictions, model files and code used to evaluate model performance are accessible at [doi:https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17379310](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17379310). Documentation of the associated data processing workflows is available via the SeaBee GitHub page.

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